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MODERN PERSPECTIVES OF QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY

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Abstract. This article is devoted to some solutions to the problems facing today's tasks of cryptography and further plans for quantum cryptography. This scientific approach analyzed the possibility of improving the quantum algorithm in quantum computers using functional spaces. The main challenges facing engineers in the development and use of quantum processors in the future are discussed, as well as the basic concepts of the qubit and new projects expected in the future by Google to achieve quantum supremacy.

Keywords: quantum, qubit, classical cryptography, quantum computers, quantum mechanics, quantum algorithm, functional spaces, Euclidean space, Hilbert space.

INTRODUCTION

Cryptography as a science appeared several thousand years ago, but its relevance is increasing today, because the problem of the security of information transmitted due to the growth of the volume of

information transmitted over the Internet and the number of participants in the network is increasing day by day. is coming out. All these problems are one of the most important issues facing cryptographers.

As far as we know, the following problems are solved with the help of cryptography, for example:

- authentication in social networks and other web resources;
- communication in instant messengers using end-to-end encryption;
- payment in online stores;
- secure data transfer between web resources or between "client" and server;
- save data on your personal computer or cloud storage;
- buying / selling cryptocurrency;
- personal digital signature;
- and others.

Currently, existing computer systems use cryptographic algorithms to solve the problems of secure data transmission. But can these algorithms hold up for quantum computers? We will try to find answers to such questions.

A quantum computer is a computing device that uses the phenomena of quantum mechanics (quantum superposition, quantum entanglement) to transfer and process data. The idea of quantum computer technology dates back to the 1980s thanks to the work of Nobel Prize-winning scientist Richard Feynman.

A quantum computer (unlike a conventional computer) does not work with bits (which can take the value 0 or 1), but with qubits, which have the values 0 and 1 at the same time. Theoretically, this allows you to process all possible cases at the same time, which means achieving a significant advantage over traditional computers in a number of algorithms.

The application of the ideas of quantum mechanics has already opened a new era in the field of cryptography, as quantum cryptography methods open up new possibilities in the field of message transmission. Prototype systems of this type are being developed[1-3].

Due to the enormous speed of prime factorization, a quantum computer can decrypt messages encrypted with the widely used RSA cryptographic algorithm. So far, this algorithm is relatively reliable, because for a classical computer, an efficient method of dividing numbers into prime factors is still unknown. For example, to enter a credit card, you need to factor hundreds of numbers into two primes (even for supercomputers, this task takes hundreds of times longer than the age of the universe). Thanks to Shor's quantum algorithm, this task will be possible if a quantum computer is built.

Currently, asymmetric cryptosystems are used to generate digital signatures and encrypt (form) symmetric keys when they are distributed over communication channels. Key distribution protocols include the Diffie-Hellman meth The idea of qubits-Quantum computing is that a quantum system of L two-level quantum elements (quantum bits, qubits) has $2L$ linearly independent states, that is, due to the principle of quantum superposition, the state space of such a quantum is a register $2L$ -dimensional Gilbert space. An operation in quantum computing corresponds to rotating the state vector

of a register in this space. Thus, a quantum computing device with size L qubits actually uses $2L$ classical states simultaneously. Physical systems implementing qubits can be any objects with two quantum states: polarization states of photons, electronic states of isolated atoms or ions, spin states of atomic nuclei, etc.

A single classical bit can be in one and only one state of 0 or 1. A quantum bit called a qubit is in a state, therefore and the digital envelope method. Among digital signature methods, RSA-like algorithms and algorithms based on the El-Gamal method, standardized in a number of countries, have found the most use. The most promising is the use of the improved method of El-Gamal digital signature, standardized in the USA and Russia in recent years. The idea of qubits-Quantum computing is that a quantum system of L two-level quantum elements (quantum bits, qubits) has $2L$ linearly independent states, that is, due to the principle of quantum superposition, the state space of such a quantum is a register $2L$ -dimensional Hilbert space. An operation in quantum computing corresponds to rotating the state vector of a register in this space. Thus, a quantum computing device with size L qubits actually uses $2L$ classical states simultaneously. Physical systems implementing qubits can be any objects with two quantum states: polarization states of photons, electronic states of isolated atoms or ions, spin states of atomic nuclei, etc.

A single classical bit can be in one and only one state of 0 or 1. A quantum bit called a qubit is in a state, therefore $|a|^2$ vs $|b|^2$ the probability of getting 0 or 1, respectively, when this condition is measured

$$|a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1$$

satisfies the equality.

Immediately after the measurement, the qubit enters the ground quantum state corresponding to the classical result.

Example:

A qubit exists in a quantum state.

In this case, the probability of getting in the measurement

$$0 - (4/5)^2 = 16/25 = 0,64,$$

$$1 - (-3/5)^2 = 9/25 = 0,36.$$

In this case, when measuring, we got 0 with a probability of 0.64. As a result of the measurement, the qubit moves to a new quantum state, that is, the next time this qubit is measured, we get 0 with unit probability (by default, the unitary operation is assumed to be the same; in real systems, this is not always the case).

Let's move on to a two-qubit system. Measuring each of them can give 0 or 1. Therefore, the system has 4 classical states: 00, 01, 10 and 11. Similar to them, the fundamental quantum states and, finally, the general quantum state of the system have the form. Now $|a|^2$ - 00 and so on. Note that

$$|a|^2 + |b|^2 + |c|^2 + |d|^2 = 1$$

as a total probability.

In the first case, it gives the measurement state, in the second, to the qubit state. We see again that the result of such a measurement cannot be written as a vector in the Hilbert state space. Such a state, in

which we do not know what the outcome will be in the first qubit, is called a mixed state. In our case, such a mixed state is called the projection of the initial state onto the second qubit and is written as a density matrix of the form ρ , where ρ is defined as the state density matrix.

In the general case, a system of L qubits has 2^L classical states (0000... (L zeros), ...00001 (L numbers), ... , 1111... (L ones)), each of which can be measured with probability 0-1.

A simplified calculation scheme in a quantum computer looks like this: a system of qubits is obtained, in which the initial state is recorded. Then the state of the system or its subsystems is changed using unitary transformations that perform certain logical operations. At the end, the value is measured and this is the result of the computer. The role of classical computer wires is played by qubits, and the role of classical computer logic blocks is played by unitary transformations. This concept of quantum processor and quantum logic gates was proposed by David Deutsch in 1989. Also, David Deutsch in 1995 discovered a universal logic block with which any quantum computation can be performed.

Using basic quantum operations, it is possible to simulate the operation of simple logic elements from which ordinary computers are built. Therefore, any problem solved now can be solved by any quantum computer and almost simultaneously [1,8].

Most modern computers work the same way: n bits of memory are stored state and changed by the processor every clock cycle. In the quantum state, an n -qubit system is in a state that is a superposition of all ground states, so changing the system affects all 2^n ground states simultaneously. Theoretically, the new scheme can work (exponentially) faster than the classical one. In practice, for example, Grover's quantum database search algorithm exhibits quadratic power compared to classical algorithms.

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According to research in the field of artificial intelligence, quantum computers are theoretically well-suited to the needs of machine learning. They manipulate large amounts of data at once and are capable of modeling neural networks of exponential size[2,3].

In 2013, Google Corporation announced the opening of a quantum research laboratory in the field of artificial intelligence[8]. The Volkswagen Group is researching the use of quantum computers to create self-driving cars and new types of batteries (using Google and D-Wave quantum computers). In November 2018, the D-Wave concern announced the development of a motion control system (with the integration of unmanned vehicles) using quantum computers[8].

In December 2015, Google experts confirmed the use of quantum effects in the D-Wave computer according to their research. However, in a "1000-qubit" computer, the qubits are organized into clusters of 8 qubits each. However, it made it possible to achieve 100 million times faster performance (compared to a conventional computer) in one of the algorithms.

Quantum computers and quantum computing are new challenges added to our information space, along with artificial intelligence, machine learning and other high-tech terms Quantum computers How do they work? In fact, the starting point of the quantum era is the year 1900, when M. Planck first put

forward the hypothesis that energy is emitted and absorbed in separate quanta (parts) rather than continuously. This idea was accepted and developed by many famous scientists of that time - Bohr, Einstein, Heisenberg, Schrödinger, which eventually led to the creation and development of a science such as quantum physics. There is a lot of good material on the Internet about the formation of quantum physics as a science, which we will not go into in detail in this article, but we can partially analyze the connections between the periods.

In addition, you can read the roadmap for the development of quantum technologies, for example, google "development of quantum technologies", for example, a bit in an ordinary computer is well known to us. It can take the values 0 or 1. It perfectly fulfills the role of a logical unit for an ordinary computer, but the qubit was invented to describe the state of a quantum object. In its limit states it is similar to 0 and 1 realizes the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, and by superposition it represents the probability distribution over the limit states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$:

$$a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle, \text{ where } a^2 + b^2 = 1$$

In this case, a and b represent the amplitudes of the probabilities, and the squares of their modules are the actual probability of obtaining the exact values of the boundary states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ if the qubit is summed with the right of measurement.

There is a concept of a universal set of gates that is sufficient to perform any quantum computation. For example, a set that includes a Hadamard gate, a phase-shift gate, a CNOT gate, and a $\pi/8$ gate is universal. They can be used to perform any quantum computation on an arbitrary set of qubits.

D-wave computers work on the principle of quantum relaxation (quantum state), can solve a very limited subclass of optimization problems, and are not suitable for implementing traditional quantum algorithms and quantum gates.

8 KB is required to store 10 qubit emulated states

20 qubit states require 8 MB to store

To store 30 qubit states, you need 8 GB

In conclusion, in this article we looked at the main period of the development of quantum computing and quantum computers, analyzed the principle of their operation, considered the main problems faced by engineers in the development and use of quantum processors, and also what is a multiqubit we got information about. So, computers are actually D-wave and Google's anticipated new project in its quest to achieve quantum supremacy.

The quantization problem is implemented by introducing a scalar or norm in Hilbert space. One of the important properties of functional analysis to visualize this space is that it conveniently maps complex functional spaces (spaces whose points are functions) into simpler, well-studied spaces, such as straight lines, using metrics, norms, and scalar multiplication. consists of learning. This idea has been working for a hundred years. In functional analysis, as a rule, functional spaces are seen as the inclusion of several interconnected different mathematical structures (for example, algebraic operations, metric, norm, scalar product, partial order). Viewing functional spaces in this way makes it possible to use various methods in functional analysis, especially analytical and topological methods.

The main task of functional analysis is to study functional spaces and the operators defined in them and to apply them in practice.

As we know from the mathematical foundations of cryptography, if we consider the Euclidean space E as a normalized space, E may or may not be complete. If E is not complete, we denote its complementary Banach space by $E^{\wedge}$ and we can simply prove that it is complete. So, as we know, the complement of Euclidean space can also be Euclidean space. Based on the above, a complete Euclidean space is called a Gilbert space. In order to carry out research in this field in the future, it is necessary to emphasize that, in a certain sense, there are enough unsolved problems in the Gilbert space.

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